

Effect of Zinc Supplementation in Sickle Cell Disease: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

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REVIEW TITLE AND BASIC DETAILS

Review title

Effect of Zinc Supplementation in Sickle Cell Disease: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

Condition or domain being studied

Sickle Cell Disease; Zinc; Placebo

Sickle cell disease (SCD) is a chronic and debilitating hematologic disorder primarily affecting populations of African, Mediterranean, Middle Eastern, and Indian descent. Patients with SCD experience severe complications such as chronic haemolytic anaemia, Vaso-occlusive crises (VOC), stroke, and multi-organ damage. The management of SCD remains challenging, with limited therapeutic options beyond supportive care and hydroxyurea therapy.

Zinc is an important element in many cellular processes, responsible for the development of T and B cell immunity. Deficiency of zinc is very common in children with SCA, due to zinc release following bone degradation in VOC and hemolysis, along with the subsequent loss of zinc in urine, zinc deficiency negatively impacts T and B cell function and cell-mediated immunity, potentially increasing the risk of infection in SCA. This systematic review and meta-analysis will provide comprehensive insights into the Effect of Zinc Supplementation in Sickle Cell Disease in real-world and clinical settings and aid clinicians in decision-making.

Rationale for the review

Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) is a genetic condition that compromises the quality of life, leading to symptoms like anemia, painful episodes, and a higher risk of infections. For those living with SCD, treatment options are often limited, mostly focusing on supportive care and medications like hydroxyurea. A common issue for individuals with SCD is zinc deficiency, which can happen due to both increased loss and difficulties in absorption. This deficiency can further weaken the immune system, cause growth delays, and lead to more health complications.

Emerging evidence has suggested that it might help reduce painful vaso-occlusive crises, improve blood counts and immune function, and lower the chances of infections.

This systematic review and meta-analysis aims to bring together the existing research on the effectiveness of zinc supplementation for SCD and provide evidence-based clinical decision-making.

Review objectives

Primary Objectives:

1. To assess the effectiveness of zinc supplementation in reducing the rate of vaso-occlusive crises (VOC) in individuals with SCD.
2. To assess the impact of zinc supplementation on haematological and immunological markers in individuals with SCD.

Keywords

Zinc supplementation; Sickle cell disease; Vaso-occlusive crisis; Placebo; Standard of care

Country

India

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Population

Included

Individuals diagnosed with sickle cell disease (SCD), including all genotypes (e.g., HbSS, HbSC, HbS/β-thalassemia).

Excluded

Patients with other hemoglobinopathies or unrelated blood disorders, unless separate SCD subgroup data is available.

Intervention(s) or exposure(s)

Included

Zinc deficiency may lead to growth issues in children with sickle cell disease (SCD). Studies suggest that zinc supplementation can improve growth and health outcomes in both children and adults with SCD

Excluded

Studies where zinc is used only as part of a supplementary therapy, unless the individual effect can be determined.

Comparator(s) or control(s)

Included

The comparator in this review includes placebo or standard-of-care treatment. Standard-of-care treatment for SCD generally consists of hydroxyurea, blood transfusions, and supportive management, such as pain control and infection prophylaxis.

Study design

Only randomized study types will be included.

Included

We will include randomised controlled trials (RCTs), to assess the effect of Zinc Supplementation in Sickle Cell Disease.

Excluded

Preclinical studies, case reports, editorials and correspondence shall be excluded.

Context

The review will include studies conducted in any healthcare setting, including hospitals, outpatient clinics, and community-based care. No geographic or income-based restrictions will be applied. Studies from both high-income and low- and middle-income countries will be included if they meet the eligibility criteria. Research conducted in controlled clinical environments, as well as real-world settings, will be considered to ensure a comprehensive evaluation of zinc's effect on SCD in diverse healthcare contexts.

TIMELINE OF THE REVIEW

Date of first submission to PROSPERO

14 April 2025

Review timeline

Start date: 15 April 2025. End date: 15 May 2025.

Date of registration in PROSPERO

21 April 2025

AVAILABILITY OF FULL PROTOCOL

Availability of full protocol

A full protocol has been written and uploaded to PROSPERO. The protocol may be accessed through this link

<https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPEROFILES/9b9be7191dc78a839b479228e7c6b467.pdf>.

SEARCHING AND SCREENING

Search for unpublished studies

Only published studies will be sought.

Main bibliographic databases that will be searched

The main databases to be searched are *MEDLINE* and *PubMed*.

Other important or specialist databases that will be searched

Google scholar

Search language restrictions

The review will only include studies published in English.

Search date restrictions

There are no search date restrictions.

Other methods of identifying studies

No other methods will be used.

Link to search strategy

A full search strategy has been uploaded to PROSPERO. The PDF may be accessed through this link

<https://www.crd.york.ac.uk/PROSPEROFILES/0324d42cb5218b13dea523bf7f4a261e.pdf>.

Selection process

Studies will be screened independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Other relevant information about searching and screening

None

DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

Data extraction from published articles and reports

Data will be extracted independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Authors will be asked to provide any required data not available in published reports.

Study datasets/IPD will be obtained from study investigators or via a data repository

Study risk of bias or quality assessment

Risk of bias will be assessed using: *Cochrane RoB-2*

Data will be assessed independently by at least two people (or person/machine combination) with a process to resolve differences.

Additional information will be sought from study investigators if required information is unclear or unavailable in the study publications/reports.

Reporting bias assessment

Risk of bias due to missing results will be assessed

Certainty assessment

Certainty assessment will be undertaken by assessing publication bias by generating funnel plot.

OUTCOMES TO BE ANALYSED

Main outcomes

1. Incidence of infection requiring hospitalisation or emergency visit.

Additional outcomes

1. Haematological response like plasma zinc, lymphocyte zinc, and granulocyte zinc from the baseline to follow-up.

2. Immunological marker in individuals with SCD: IL-2 production.

3. Incidence of Serious Adverse Events or SCA-related complications, including vaso-occlusive episodes (VOEs)

PLANNED DATA SYNTHESIS

Strategy for data synthesis

A meta-analysis will be conducted if at least two studies report comparable outcomes. For dichotomous outcomes, risk ratios (RR) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) will be calculated, while for continuous outcomes, mean differences (MD) or standardised mean differences (SMD) with 95% CIs will be used.

A random-effects model (REM) will be applied to account for between-study variability. Heterogeneity will be assessed using the I^2 statistic, categorised as low (0–50%), medium (50–70%), or high (75–100%). If substantial heterogeneity ($I^2 > 50%$) is detected, potential sources will be explored through subgroup analyses based on study design, disease severity, and zinc dosage. Sensitivity analyses will be performed by excluding studies with a high risk of bias to assess their impact on pooled estimates.

If meta-analysis is not feasible due to substantial heterogeneity or limited data, a narrative synthesis will be conducted, summarising key study characteristics, efficacy, and safety findings. Data analysis will be performed using Review Manager (RevMan) version 5 software

CURRENT REVIEW STAGE

Stage of the review at this submission

Review stage	Started	Completed
Pilot work	✓	✓
Formal searching/study identification	✓	✓
Screening search results against inclusion criteria	✓	
Data extraction or receipt of IPD		
Risk of bias/quality assessment		
Data synthesis		

Review status

The review is currently planned or ongoing.

Publication of review results

Results of the review will be published.

REVIEW AFFILIATION, FUNDING AND PEER REVIEW

Review team members

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No conflict of interest declared.

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No conflict of interest declared.

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No conflict of interest declared.

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Funding source

Review has no funding and no agreed support from an academic institution and is done in authors' own time.

Peer review

There has been no peer review of this planned review.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Review conflict of interest

Declared individual interests are recorded under team member details.. No additional interests are recorded for this review.

Medical Subject Headings

Adult; Anemia, Sickle Cell; Child; Hematologic Diseases; Hemoglobinopathies; Hemolysis; Humans; Hydroxyurea; Immunity, Cellular; Stroke; Zinc

SIMILAR REVIEWS

Check for similar records already in PROSPERO

PROSPERO identified a number of existing PROSPERO records that were similar to this one (last check made on 14 April 2025). These are shown below along with the reasons given by that the review team for the reviews being different and/or proceeding.

- Efficacy and Safety of Mitapivat in Sickle Cell Disease: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis [published 3 March 2025] [CRD420251000061]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Vaso-Occlusive Crises in Sickle Cell Disease: Evaluating Pharmacodynamics, Efficacy, and Safety of Therapeutic Options as Reported in Randomized Controlled Trials [published 5 March 2025] [CRD420251004494]. The review was judged **not to be similar**
- Iron Deficiency Anemia (IDA) and the Response of Iron Supplementation in Sickle Cell Disorders (SCDs): A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis [published 23 September 2023] [CRD42023462914]. The review was judged **not to be similar**

PROSPERO version history

- [Version 1.0, published 21 Apr 2025](#)

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